

Flame retardancy and fire mechanical properties for natural fiber/polymer composite: A review

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Abstract: The vulnerability against heat and fire for natural fibers presents a great challenge for their replacement of traditional fiber reinforcements in composite materials. Natural fiber/polymer composites (NFCs) are considered as potential candidates in engineering applications due to their environmental friendliness and low-impact sourcing. Hence, suitable approaches need to be employed to enhance the fire safety of NFCs. In this review, the latest understanding of the flammability and thermal properties for natural fibers was summarized and discussed, with special focus on their interaction with polymer matrix in fire behavior. Furthermore, the latest development of flame-retardant approaches for NFCs was reviewed by covering both flame retardancy and fire structural integrity. Finally, outlook and perspectives regarding fire-safe of NFCs were proposed, providing insight into the further development of NFCs.

Keywords: Natural fiber/polymer composite; flame retardancy; fire mechanical properties

Graphical abstract

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Abbreviations

AZ	Ammonium zeolite	APTES	Aminopropyltriethoxysilane
ATH	Aluminum trihydrate	APP	Ammonium polyphosphate
AlPi	Aluminum diethyl phosphinate	BF	Basalt fiber
CCT	Cone calorimeter test	DMMP	Dimethyl methylphosphonate
DOPO	9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide	DAP	Diammonium phosphate
DVP	Dimethyl vinyl phosphonates	EG	Expandable graphite
FRs	Flame retardants	FRCs	Fiber-reinforced polymer composites
GnP	Graphene nanoplate	HDPE	High-density polyethylene
h-BN	Hexagonal boron nitride	IFR	Intumescent flame retardant
IFSS	Interfacial shear strength	LbL	Layer-by-layer
LCM	Liquid composite molding	LOI	Limiting oxygen index
MMT	Montmorillonite	MCA	Melamine cyanurate
MAP	Mono ammonium phosphate	MHO	Magnesium hydroxide
MCC	Microcrystalline cellulose	NFCs	Natural fiber/polymer composites

PP	Polypropylene	PEI	Polyethyleneimine
PA	Phytic acid	PLA	Polylactic acid
PEC	Polyelectrolyte complex	PMMA	Poly methyl methacrylate
SA	Sodium alginate	TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
TSP	Total smoke production	TTI	Time-to-ignition
THR	Total heat release	UA	Urea
UPR	Unsaturated Polyester Resin	ZB	Zinc borate
ZHO	Zirconium hydroxide		

1. Introduction

Natural fiber/ polymer composites (NFCs) have gained increasing attention mainly due to their natural abundance, low density, and biodegradability^[1-3]. According to the extraction resources, natural fibers can be classified into different class as plant fibers, mineral fibers and animal fibers, as shown in Scheme 1. Among them, plant fibers and mineral fibers are widely used in engineering materials, especially in automotive & aerospace, civil engineering, sports and leisure sectors^[4]. Similar to conventional reinforcement fibers such as glass, carbon and aramid fiber, NFCs show improved mechanical properties like strength and modulus, offering high specific strength and light weight advantages.^[5] Physical and mechanical properties of natural fibers can be ranged among a wide spectrum of values as shown in Table 1. Nevertheless, due to their intrinsic flammability from polymer matrix and mostly fibers, NFCs endorses an even greater danger compared to traditional fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRCs) when encountering fire hazards.^[6] This is arguably one of the key limitations for NFRCs as compared to other reinforced composite materials.

Scheme 1. Classification of natural fibers.^[7, 8]

Plant fibers such as flax, hemp, ramie, kenaf, jute, sisal, abaca, coir, fruit fiber etc.^[8, 9] are the most used type of natural fiber for NFCs. Known also as lignocellulosic fiber, plant fibers are mainly composed of cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin and other components, which endow the plant fiber with inherent flammability. Compared with plant fiber, mineral fiber, like conventional glass and carbon fibers, shows a drastic difference in terms of thermal decomposition and flammability, with great influence on the fire safety in NFCs. Besides, due to animal fiber currently being hardly used as reinforcement in NCFs as engineering usage, it has not covered in this review.

In addition, polymeric matrix used in NFCs ranges from thermosets (epoxy, unsaturated polyester, or vinyl ester, phenolic etc.) to thermoplastics (Polylactic acid (PLA), Polypropylene (PP), Polyamide, High-density polyethylene (HDPE) etc.) due to their well-known good mechanical behavior as well as resistance to chemicals and harsh environments. However, the interaction between polymer matrix and natural fiber also poses a great influence on the fire behavior in NFCs which further complicates the challenge for flame retardancy of NFCs.

Table 1. Typical properties of natural fibers and their comparison with traditional reinforcement fibers. Reproduced with permission from ^[9]. Copyright 2020, Elsevier.

Fiber	Density (g /cm³)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Specific modulus (GPa/(kg/m³))	Elongation at break (%)
Flax	1.53	745-1145	44-61	35	2.07
Kenaf	1.4-1.5	223-930	15-53	24	1.5-2.7
Hemp	1.48	690	70	47	1.6
Jute	1.3	393-773	27	21	1.5-1.8
Ramie	1.5	560	25	17	2.5
Cotton	1.5-1.6	287-800	6-13	6	3-10
Basalt	2.7	2130	93	47	2
Carbon (Hexcel AS4)	1.8	4330	231	129	1.8
E-glass	2.5-2.6	2000-3500	70-76	29	1.8-4.8
S-glass	2.5	4570	86	34	2.8

Compared to the reports that intensively covered the topics of NFCs focusing in design^[8], manufacturing^[10], mechanical properties^[11] and recycling^[12, 13] and others^[8-10, 14-17], fewer reports focused on the recent investigations for the flammability and methodologies for improving fire safety and fire mechanical properties for NFCs, especially during the last five years. Up to now, numerous efforts have been made to explore flame-retardant approaches by exploiting the unique features of different natural fibers as well as the polymer matrix. In general, the approaches to impart flame retardancy and fire safety of FRCs can be categorized into either modification on polymer matrix, functionalization of fiber surface or providing fire protective surface finishing.^[18] Clearly each approach possess its own advantages and disadvantages, which will be discussed throughout this work. Some excellent review papers^[19, 20] or book chapters^[21] have covered certain aspects of flame-retardant natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites before 2019, which inspired the current ongoing research and development of this topic.

Hence, this review aims to summarize and analyze the latest development, outlook, and challenges of flame retarded NFCs during the last five years. First, the thermal and flammability properties of natural fibers and their' interaction with polymer matrix in combustions were discussed and summarized. Then, the recent development for improving the fire safety of NFCs was introduced and discussed, describing each methodology and their advantages and disadvantages. Thereafter, a discussion was also covered about the recent and former research and investigation regarding the mechanical behavior of NFCs under fire loads is provided. Finally, future perspectives and challenges on the development of new flame-retardant NFCs are proposed.

2. Flammability and thermal properties of natural fibers

The flammability of natural fibers and their contribution to fire hazards are closely associated with their' thermal decomposition, heat release as well as the ability to char.^[22] The understanding of the thermal and flammability of natural fibers lies as the foundation for imparting fire safety to natural fiber composites. Hence, this section aimed to summarize the knowledge gained from previous research, especially the difference between natural and traditional fibers, to fulfill the goal of flame-retardancy.

2.1. Thermal properties of natural fibers

Flammable volatiles derived from the thermal decomposition of natural fibers add fuel to maintain the chain reaction and promote continuous combustion during the burning of NFCs. The plant fibers possessed a hierarchical structure ranging from macroscopic scale to molecular scale^[23], as shown in Figure 1 (a). As indicated by the known name of lignocellulosic fiber, most plant fibers are mainly composed of varied fractions of hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin, pectin etc., as shown in Figure 1 (b)^[24]. Among them, hemicellulose is the least thermally stable and starts decomposing at 200 °C. Cellulose decomposes around 350 °C, while lignin decomposes in a wide range of temperatures from 200 to 600 °C.^[25] A typical thermogravimetric decomposition process of natural fibers was shown in Figure 1 (c).^[26] It was found that two competitive routes coexist during the thermal decomposition of cellulose as depolymerization and dehydration. Depolymerization gave rise to the formation of levoglucosan, which contributes more flammable volatiles and less char compared to the route of dehydration^[26-28]. It was suggested that the thermal stability and decomposition of natural fibers depend mainly on their chemical composition as well as physical structure, such as the degree of polymerization and fibrillar orientation in plant fibers.^[21] Yao^[29] found that most

natural fibers experienced 60% thermal decomposition between temperatures 215~310 °C with an apparent activation energy of 160-170 kJ/mol.

Compared to plant fiber which decomposes and loses mass substantially under air atmosphere, like mineral fiber, like basalt fibers are non-combustible like glass fiber.^[14] According to Hao^[30], basalt fiber and glass fiber both decomposed around 200°C and displayed a single-step decomposition pattern. Nonetheless basalt fiber experienced less mass loss compared to glass fiber, which demonstrates the high thermal stability and fire resistance of mineral fibers.

Figure 1. (a) Graphical illustration of a hierarchical structure of flax fiber, from macroscopic to molecular scale. Reproduced with permission from reference^[23]. Copyrights 2019 Elsevier. (b) Chemical composition of some selected natural fibers. (c) The typical thermogravimetric decomposition process of natural fibers. Reproduced with permission from reference^[26] Copyrights 2013 Elsevier.

Compared with widely used carbon or glass fiber, natural fiber, especially plant fibers, possess the capability of charring. However, the intrinsic residue value of plant fibers is limited measured by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in some cases^[28, 31]. The decomposition chemistry can be largely influenced by its composition and the addition of flame retardants (FRs). The three main components of plant fiber have different abilities to char, in which lignin generally has a high char tendency mainly due to its polyaromatic structure. Nevertheless, there is no clear linear mixture relationship between the char residue value and the composition of plant fiber. It was

assumed that both the composition and structure (crystallinity, interchain distance, molecular weight, orientation) played in the role of pyrolysis of plant fibers.^[21] Unlike plant fibers, mineral fiber such as basalt fibers are deemed noncombustible with a much higher melting temperature compared to even glass fiber, thereby possessing little ability of charring.

The contribution to flame by combustion of plant fiber itself releases heat around 8-12 kJ per gram, compared to widely used thermoplastic or thermosets matrices.^[32] So they generally showed lower the heat release and flammability of NFCs with increasing fiber contents.

Furthermore, FRCs are known to be employed in structural loading scenarios mainly due to their high specific strength-to-weight ratio. Hence, the concept of fire safety cannot be constrained within the hazards related to the combustion of flammable substances. Upon heat and fire damage, polymer matrix and some reinforcement fiber will soften, melt/decompose and eventually decompose and be ignited, this will lead to structural failure of polymer composites which pose an even greater risk due to structural collapse.^[33-35] Due to the low thermal stability and glass transition temperatures of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin, plant fiber generally undergoes a quick reduction of mechanical properties during high temperatures and fire, which eventually leads to structural collapse.^[36, 37] Hence, the low fire structural stability of plant fiber limits its usage for the application involving structural loading. Meanwhile, mineral fiber brings more interest in high-temperature application due to its high softening temperature and non-combustibility. Basalt fiber reflects in the preservation of good mechanical properties at high temperatures thanks to their high thermal stability in the range of from 200 °C to 700 °C. The softening temperature for basalt fibers is in

the order of 960 °C, resulting in greater than that of E-glass fibers by about 15%. Sim et al.^[38] found that the basalt fiber kept about 90% of the normal temperature strength after exposure at 600°C for two hours. Whereas the carbon and the glass fibers were either being oxidized or melted without maintaining their volumetric integrity at 1200°C.^[39]

2.2. Influence of fiber constituents on fire safety of composites

Traditional fiber reinforcements demonstrated a diluent effect mainly due to most of them being incombustible or hardly flammable, leading to a lower content of fuels for fire hazards. The low heat release of plant fibers itself and the none combustibility of mineral fiber tended to lower heat release when the higher contents of natural fiber were added into the polymer matrix.^[21] For instance, Khuntia et al.^[40] recently found out that by increasing short coir fiber content in PP from 10 to 30wt%, the UL 94 vertical burning rating were improved from V-2 to V-0 (3mm thickness). Suriani et al.^[41] fabricated a kenaf/polyester hybrid yarn-reinforced epoxy composite with 5wt% of Magnesium hydroxide (MHO) and different kenaf content (0, 20, 35, 50wt%). The higher kenaf fiber brought lower flammability in terms of average burning rate and tensile strength. In their work, the author also investigated the different contents of oil palm empty fruit bunches fiber filled epoxy composite with the same 5wt% MHO and found similar results.^[42] However, when combined with most heat-resistant polymer matrices such as cyanate ester, polybenzoxazine or polyfurfuryl alcohol, the combustion of plant fibers might contribute to an increase for heat release.

Different physiochemical effects are influencing the fire behavior of NFCs, especially considering fiber-matrix interaction during the combustion process. As shown in Figure 2 (a), the wick effect is a physicochemical phenomenon in which, at a

high temperature, a polymer melt is adsorbed on the fiber's surface and generates surface tension-driven flow from the interfacial region to the flaming zone, therefore accelerating the fuel supply and intensifying the combustion.^[43] These effects are predominant in a thermoplastic matrix, which brings challenges to its flame retardation.^[44, 45] Wick effects were widely reported among glass fiber reinforced composites^[46], while some reports of wick effects on plant fiber, such as bamboo fibers and flax fibers were also discussed recently^[47-49].

Figure 2. (a) Scheme demonstration of wick effects. Reproduced with permission from reference^[44]. Copyright 2013 Royal Society of Chemistry. (b) Influence of unidirectional and quasi-isotropic stacking sequences and samples thickness on the heat release behavior of composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[50]. Copyright 2012 Wiley. Charring suppressing effects demonstrated by comparing HRR and THR curves of DGEBA/DMC (filled squares), DGEBA/DMC+DOPI (open squares), RTM6 (filled circles) and RTM6+DOPI (open circles) (c1, c2) and carbon fiber reinforced resin with DGEBA/DMC-CF (filled squares), DGEBA/DMC-CF+DOPI (open squares), RTM6-CF (filled circles) and RTM6-CF+DOPI (open circles) (d1, d2) at an external heat flux of 50 kW/m². Reproduced with permission from reference^[51]. Copyright 2011 Wiley. Scheme for out-of-plane angle samples (e1) and its influence on heat release behavior (e2). Reproduced with permission from reference^[52]. Copyright 2018 Wiley.

The short fiber (usually no longer than 5~10 mm) contributes to the barrier effects during combustion if combined with a high-charring polymer matrix or charring-promoting FRs.^[53] Mineral fibers were suggested to enhance the rigidity and compactness of char layer during combustion, which inhibits thermal and mass transfer, thereby lowering fire risks. Liu et al.^[54] investigated the influence of sepiolite addition on the intumescent flame retardant (IFR)/PP system. The results found that with an

appropriate amount of sepiolite, the mechanical properties and flame retardancy were both improved due to improved intumescent effects and a more compact char layer.

The fiber reinforcement architecture also possess an impact on burning behavior and fire hazards as well. The stacking sequence (such as unidirectional or quasi-isotropic layup) and fiber preform (chopped strand mat or woven roving)^[55] played a role such as delamination^[50], which often causes unsteady burning as shown in Figure 2 (b). As can be seen in Figure 2 (e1, e2), the heat release behavior drastically changed when the out-of-plane angle increased from 0° to 90°, demonstrating the barrier effects introduced by fiber.^[52] However, most of the studies were focused on inert carbon fiber-reinforced composites. Hence, more study is needed if natural fiber, such as flammable plant fiber was used as reinforcements or fillers.

It was noteworthy that the continuous fiber is suggested to alter the charring behavior and retards the fire-retardant efficiency of traditional FRs, especially for which mainly works in the condensed phase.^[56] As shown in Figure 2 (c1, c2, d1, d2), the introduction of FRs in two epoxy systems showed a higher reduction in peak heat release rate (PHRR) for resin individually compared to carbon fiber/epoxy composites. One suggestion was that the rigid fiber, especially from noncombustible fiber reinforcement with high surface area, inhibits the charring process and prevents the formation of a compact char layer, which leaves cracks and pores as channels for heat and mass transfer.^[51, 57] This effect might be less obvious in terms of plant fiber-reinforced polymer composite due to its early decomposition and charring capabilities, while detailed investigation remains to be explored.

The stacking sequence and orientation are shown to play significant roles in terms of fire structural integrity too. Grigoriou et al.^[58] investigated the effects of ply stacking

pattern on the structural survivability of quasi-isotropic carbon-epoxy composites subjected to both tension and compression under fire. It was found that laminates, with 0° middle piles heated up quicker, experienced more heat-induced delamination compared to those composites with 45° middle plies, which in turn decreased the heat transfer through-thickness and confined heat to the surface exposed to fire. Their research also found that the ply stacking pattern exerted more influence on softening rate and failure time when subject to tension axial loading than axial compression loading. While the mechanical properties of fibers, stacking sequence mainly dictates fibre-dominated mechanical properties with resin shows the limited contribution to mechanical integrity when no fire hazard is initiated, the polymer matrix seems to play a much higher role in mechanical integrity when subjected to simultaneously fire damage. In addition, most efforts on the fire structural response of polymer composites were focused on glass or carbon fiber-reinforced monolithic or sandwich composites. Only a few efforts^[59, 60] have explored this topic in NFCs.

The choices to enhance fire retardancy are also limited by the matrix type, processing temperature window and manufacturing process. Solid FRs are suitable for processes such as wet-layup, pultrusion, filament winding, inject molding etc., but pose greater challenge when employed in liquid composite moulding (LCM) processes, no matter whether traditional or natural fiber is used.^[61] In conclusion, the need for flame retardation of NFCs is urgent mainly due to its unique challenges, with special attention needing to be paid to the manufacturing process, final parts performance and corresponding regulatory standards.

3. Flame-retardant strategy

In view of the unique challenges when it comes to impart flame retardancy and fire safety to the NFCs, increasing efforts are being made to solve these ever-changing problems by incorporation of flame-retardant moieties in recent decades. There are abundant flame retardants in the industrial market, while newly designed and synthesized FRs are being proposed each year.^[62, 63] According to their chemical composition, FRs can be mainly categorized into halogen-containing substances, phosphorus-containing compounds (red phosphorus, phosphates, phosphinates, phosphites, phosphonates, phosphazene, etc.)^[64], metal hydroxides (aluminum, magnesium, calcium, zirconium, etc.), silicon-based FRs (silicon oxide, silicate-based minerals, organic silicon-based FRs, etc.) nitrogen-based flame retardants, boron-containing FRs, metal hydroxides) based FRs as well as intumescent flame retardants based on multicomponent FRs. What's more, hybrid or nano FRs^[64-66] as well as biobased FRs, have gained increasing interest, especially from researchers, mainly due to their high potential in both efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Scheme 2. Flame-retardant strategies for introducing FRs in NFCs.

According to the methodologies by which FRs were introduced in NFCs, three categories can be classified as modification of resin either by additive or reactive FRs,

surface treatment of the reinforcing fibers and applying fire protective coating on the surface of NCFs as shown in Scheme 2.

3.1. Modification of polymer matrix

Modification of the resin matrices has been one of the most popular and straightforward methods. Abundant research concerning flame-retardant bulky polymer and traditional fiber-filled or reinforced polymer composites^[67-69] can be drawn to inspire the research of fire-proofing NFCs. Earlier efforts using this method can be traced decades ago^[19], while recent research and developments within the last five years will be discussed here with summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. The recent development on modification of resin and combined approaches.

Fiber type	Surface treatment	FRs	Matrix	Flame retardancy	References
Flax unidirectional fabric 60wt%	No	SiO ₂ @PDA	Epoxy	LOI: +13.9%; PHRR: -14.2%; THR: -6.9%.	[70]
Flax woven fabric 30v%	No	APP based FRs	Epoxy and PP	PHRR: -60.5% and -55.4%; THR: -55.7% and -37%.	[71]
20-40μm ramie short fiber	No	AlPi, MCA and silica	PLA	LOI: +73.7%; UL-94: V0; PHRR: -19.4%; THR: -13.5%.	[72]
Flax unidirectional	No	DMPP and MMT	Phenolic resin	LOI: +50.3%; UL 94: V0; PHRR: -67.4%; THR: -61.3%	[73]
4~6mm Short Coir fiber	No	No	PP	UL-94: V0;	[40]
Jute woven fabric	No	ATH and ZTO	UPR	UL-94: HB; PHRR: -13.4%; THR: -10.8%.	[74]
Flax unidirectional fabric 30 vol%	No	AlPi and DOPO	Epoxy	PHRR: -13.2% and -9.2%; THR: -14.6% and -16.0%	[75]

Kenaf/PET hybrid	No	MHO	Epoxy	Horizontal burning rate: -34.3%.	[41]
Palm fiber/PET	No	MHO	Epoxy	Horizontal burning rate: -48.2%.	[42]
Basalt short fiber	Silane treatment	APP	Epoxy	LOI: +13.4%; UL 94: V0; PHRR: -55.7%; THR: -38.5%. PHRR: -63.5%	[76]
Hemp fiber mat	No	APP and ATH	Epoxy	and -22.2%; THR: -35.9% and -6.25%	[77]
Short Flax fiber 20~30wt%	No	APP and GnP	PP	PHRR: -42.7%; THR: -26.6%.	[78]
Plain woven Flax fabric	FR treatment	APP based IFR	PLA	LOI: +66.6%; UL 94: V0; LOI: +36.3%;	[79]
Short wood fiber	No	NiPO and APP	PLA	UL 94: V2; PHRR: -25.6%; THR: -22.0%.	[80]
Fruit bunch short fiber mat 20wt%	No	APP and ZB	Epoxy	FAR vertical burning passed. LOI: +19.2%;	[81]
Microcrystalline cellulose	No	AZ and	HDPE	horizontal burning rate: -17.9%.	[82]
Flax woven fabric	No	APP and ATH	Epoxy	LOI: +42.3% and +15.0%; UL 94: V0 and NR.	[83]
Short kenaf fiber	No	APP and wool fiber	PP	LOI: +42.3% and +15.0%; UL 94: V0 and NR.	[84]
Plain weave ramie fabric	h-BN surface treatment	PCTA	UPR	UL 94: NR; PHRR: -54.3%; THR: -13.4%.	[85]
Short hemp fiber	CaOH growth	APP	PP	LOI: +11.0%; UL 94: V0.	[86]
Short flax and wool fiber	No	Talc and APP	PP	PHRR: -43.9%; THR: -15.8%. UL 94: NR.	[87]
Short fruit fiber 20wt%	Some alkaline treat	EG	Epoxy	FAR vertical burning passed.	[88]
Short fruit fiber mat 18wt%	No	ATH and APP	Epoxy	FAR vertical burning passed.	[89]

Ramie fabric	P, N containing silane	APP	UP	PHRR: -42.2%; THR: -33.6%; UL 94: V0.	[90]
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3.1.1. Modification on thermoplastic matrix

Thermoplastic matrix is often inherently reprocessible due to their melting behavior, which attracts more interest by offering higher end-of-life value when working with natural fibers. As shown in Figure 3 (a), Kim et al.^[87] introduced talc and APP-based IFR to short flax fiber/PP composites for investigating its influence on flammability and mechanical properties. It was found that 15wt% IFR individually reduced PHRR and total heat release (THR) by 42% and 8% at 50kW/m². While the addition of 7wt% talc provided a slight improvement in terms of flame retardancy, none of them passed the vertical burning tests (UL 94). Besides, the addition of IFR reduced the tensile and flexural strength of composites, while the addition of talc provided mechanical improvements compared to that of NFCs without FRs.

Subasinghe et al.^[84] combined APP with other additives in the 30wt% kenaf short fiber filled PP composites as shown in Figure 3 (b) to explore about FRs interaction. Under 50 kW/m² external heat flux, the introduction of 20wt% APP brought down PHRR and THR by around 50% and 20%. But the introduction of APP promoted the early decomposition of the composite while no rating was achieved during UL 94 test. In addition, 3wt% of wool fiber or UV ray stabilizer and colorant combination (UVC) brought slight improvements in terms of both cone calorimeter test (CCT) and UL 94 results.

Figure 3. HRR curves of flax/PP and wool/PP composites with 14wt% IFR and 7wt% Talc. Reproduced with permission from reference^[87]. HRR curves and Copyright 2017 Elsevier. (b) HRR and THR curves of kenaf/PP composites with 20wt% APP and two types of synergists. Reproduced with permission from reference^[84]. Copyright 2018 Elsevier. Reproduced with permission from reference^[72] Copyright 2022 Wiley. (c1) HRR and (c2) THR curves of ramie/PLA composites with AlPi, MCA and nano SiO₂ FRs. Reproduced with permission from reference^[72] Copy rights 2022 Wiley. (d) LOI values of HDPE resin and MCC/HDPE composites modified FRs of AZ and APP. Reproduced with permission from reference^[82] Copyright 2019 Elsevier.

Zhan et al.^[72] introduced multicomponent FRs containing AlPi, melamine cyanurate (MCA) and silane-modified silicon oxide into 20wt% short ramie fiber-filled PLA composite. The varying ratio of three FRs was screened for flammability and mechanical properties. It was found that with only AlPi or MCA added into the laminate, no V0 rating in UL 94 was achieved. Although the introduction of silicon oxide decreased the limiting oxygen index (LOI) value slightly, an optimized formulation between AlPi, MCA and silicon oxide brought down even lower PHRR and THR, as shown in Figure 3 (c1, c2) while increasing char value after flameout of CCT (50 kW/m²), indicating the synergistic barrier effects. Synergistic effects from different FRs were demonstrated by Cavdar et al.^[82] using mono ammonium phosphate (MAP) and ammonium zeolite (AZ) or natural zeolite in the the15wt% microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) filled HDPE composites. The LOI value showed slight improvement while the horizontal burning rate slowed up to 64%, as shown in Figure 3 (d).

Khalili et al.^[81] studied the effects of zinc borate (ZB) interplay with either APP and ATH as FRs for fruit bunch fiber-based mat-reinforced PLA composites. It was found that the formulation with 10t% APP and 5wt% ZB passed the vertical Bunsen burner test with decreased gross heat release per gram. In terms of mechanical properties, flexural properties showed few changes, while tensile strength and elongation at breaks were reduced to a certain extent.

Tawiah et al.^[91] designed and synthesized a Phenylphosphonic FR (named P-TAB) and used it for PLA biocomposites with recycled wool fibers loadings ranging from 5wt% to 20wt%. It was found that with 3wt% of P-TAB and 20wt% of wool fibers LOI value was increased by 46.2% compared to that of neat PLA. V0 rating was also achieved. At heat flux of 35 kW/m², CCT results showed 26.0% reduction of PHRR and 42.8% reduction of THR compared to that of neat PLA, demonstrating the promising synergistic effect of wool fiber and P-TAB.

3.1.2. Modification on thermoset matrix

Thermoset polymer matrix has been long used for manufacturing FRCs with continuous fiber reinforcement, mainly due to their friendliness to impregnating, alongside the wetting of fiber reinforcement during the manufacturing process. Khalili et al.^[88, 89] investigated the flame retardancy of expandable graphite (EG), ammonium polyphosphate (APP), aluminum trihydrate (ATH) and their synergy when used in short fruit fiber-filled epoxy composites with fiber content around 20wt%. The increasing of EG content improved its flame retardancy with slight mechanical reduction. In another work, short fruit fiber/epoxy composites were flame-retarded by ATH/APP hybrid. It was found that ATH itself hardly provided flame retardancy (when used less than 15wt%), while a combination of 10wt% ATH and 5wt% APP hybrid demonstrated the

best flame retardancy within the tested groups. Mechanical reductions of modified NFCs were also found when using these three widely commercial FRs.

Bachtiar et al.^[83] investigated the effects of either melamine resin micro-encapsulated APP or ATH for the plain woven flax fabric reinforced epoxy composites. It was found that APP and ATH alone showed limited improvement in terms of LOI and UL 94 test results even if FRs content was more than 30wt%.

Campana et al.^[75] introduced aluminum diethyl phosphinate (AlPi) and 9,10-dihydro-9-oxa-10phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide (DOPO) separately into the unidirectional flax fiber reinforced epoxy composites with fiber volume ratio of 30vol%. By keeping phosphorus content at 2wt% with respect to the polymer, the content of AlPi and DOPO were 9.5wt% and 13.9wt%. As shown in Figure 4 (a), the laminate with AlPi showed a better reduction of PHRR and higher char yield value compared to that of composite with DOPO, with similar THR value output collected. However, DOPO showed a better performance in terms of longitudinal modulus and tensile strength.

Kim et al.^[71] compared the flame retardant efficiency of one FR composed of melamine-coated APP in both PP and epoxy resin matrix reinforced by flax woven baric (30vol%). It was found that this APP-based FR was more effective in epoxy resin than PP resin. In another work, Guo et al.^[76] investigated the efficiency of APP-based FR when used in short basalt fibre-filled epoxy composite. The amount of APP was around 14 Phr with respect to epoxy resin. The LOI value showed slight improvement with the V0 rating of the vertical burning test. Under external heat flux of 50 kW/m², the PHRR and THR of the modified composite showed a reduction of more than 50%, exemplifying good flame retardancy, as shown in Figure 4 (b).

Basnayake et al.^[77] prepared a hemp fibre-based nonwoven mat (~15wt%) reinforced epoxy composites with 4.5, 9, 13.5wt% of APP and ATH separately. The ignition and burning behaviour were investigated under four heat fluxes of 20, 35, 50, 70 kW/m². It was found that ATH incorporation increased the thermal inertia of the composite, which was higher than that of APP-added laminate. This explained the longer delay of time-to-ignition (T_{ig}) when using ATH as additives. The calculated thermal response parameter showed that the T_{ig} of laminate with ATH was more sensitive to the increase of heat flux than that of APP one. In terms of retarding the heat release, the APP showed better efficiency than ATH, as shown in Figure 4 (c). Thiyaгу et al.^[92] prepared glass/ramie hybrid fabric reinforced epoxy composite with varying content of APP (10, 15, 20wt%). With over 10wt% APP, both vertical and horizontal burning achieved the highest rating in terms of flammability.

Figure 4. (a)HRR curve of 30vol% flax/epoxy with FRs of 9.5wt% AlPi and 13.9wt% DOPO. Reproduced with permission from reference^[75]. Copyright 2022 MDPI. (b) HRR and THR curve of flax/epoxy with and without APP (FEP, FEPA) as well as flax/PP with and without APP (FPP, FPPA). Reproduced with permission from reference^[71] Copyright 2023 Wiley. (c) HRR curves for hemp/epoxy composites with 4.5, 9, 13.5wt% of ATH or APP. Reproduced with permission from reference^[77] Copyright 2021 Elsevier. (d) Graphical abstract for

demonstration of nano ATH and ZHO FRs on their influence on various properties of jute/UPR composites. Reproduced with permission from reference [74]. Copyright 2022 Springer Nature.

As shown in Figure 5 (a), Wei et al.^[70] synthesized a novel polydopamine (PDA) coated silicon oxide nanosized FR named SiO₂@PDA and investigated its influence in both fire safety and mechanical properties of epoxy composite reinforced by 60wt% of flax fabric. The PDA-based nanocoating on SiO₂ provided a better dispersion of nanosized FR, which in turn generated a more compact and graphitized char layer there by showing higher LOI value with lower PHRR and THR results compared to those for laminate with only pristine SiO₂ fillers.

Figure 5. (a) Scheme for the synthesis of PDA@SiO₂ nano FRs used in flax/epoxy composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[70]. Copyrights 2023 Springer Nature. HRR (b1) and THR (b2) curves of Reproduced with permission from reference^[78]. Copyrights 2021 MDPI. (c) Graphical abstract for demonstration of Ni-PO nano FRs used in wood fiber/PLA composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[80]. Copyrights 2019 American Society of Chemistry.

Ali et al.^[78] discussed the influence of graphene nanoplate (GnP) introduction of APP-based intumescent (15wt%) filled PP composite with 20~30wt% short flax fiber as shown in Figure 5 (b1, b2). The incorporation of APP significantly decreased the fire hazards of flax fiber-filled PP in terms of CCT results. The addition of GnP improved

the CCT results to a certain extent, which was suggested due to the enhancement of the integrity of the char layer during combustion. In terms of mechanical properties, the low GnP ratio achieved improvement for strength and modulus of tensile and flexural tests, while GnP content above 1wt% brought adverse effects.

As shown in Figure 5 (c), Zhang et al.^[80] prepared a novel nano-micro hybrid FR (Ni-PO) containing nickel and phosphate green chemistry approach. The synergy between APP and Ni-PO in 25wt% wood fiber-filled PLA composites was investigated by fixing the total FRs amount as 10wt%. The UL 94 rating was increased to a V1 rating with the highest LOI value when the ratio of APP: Ni-PO was 9:1. This phenomenon was also found in CCT, suggesting the synergistic role of Ni-PO with APP as mainly flame-retardant moieties. Nevertheless, the increase in Ni-PO ratio showed an improvement in tensile strength, modulus as well as impact strength compared to those properties for laminates with only APP.

Ejaz^[74] employed nanosized FRs (ATH with zirconium hydroxide (ZHO) nanoparticles) and explored their synergistic effect in 40wt% jute woven fabric reinforced UPR composite. The increasing of ATH or ZHO nanoparticles brought down flammability, while an optimal percent of 3wt% was found to be the optimal amount for mechanical properties. As shown in Figure 4 (d), in terms of heat release, 4wt% of ATH or ZHO decreased PHRR by around 15%, and similar results were achieved in the formulation in which 1.5wt% of both ATH and ZHO were used.

Adding FRs or incorporating reactive FRs into polymer networks have been the most popular methods for flame retardant NFCs. In contrast, various issues need to be reconsidered within this methodology. As mentioned above, the charring behavior may be suppressed when using FRs that mainly work in condensed phase in the polymer

matrix. The manufacturing methods also play a vital role in terms of selection of FRs when it comes to the processing of NFCs. The functional temperature or decomposition temperature of additive FRs needs to be evaluated before processing, especially for thermoplastic polymers. In terms of the LCM process for composite manufacturing, it has been reported that oversized solid FRs may be filtered by fiber preform, especially short fiber mats or woven fabric.^[93-95] In addition, the addition of reactive or additive FRs may alter the curing kinetics during the solidification of thermoset, which may pose a negative influence on certain parameters like mixed viscosity, gel time, and permeability.

3.2. Functionalization of fiber surface

Fiber, which has a high surface area compared to resin matrix offers the potential to locate FRs on its surface without disruption of resin matrix. Hence, another method to impart flame retardancy is by functionalization of fiber surface. Dry fibers are often used in different preforms, such as yarns, bundles, mats, short and long fibers, as well as continuous woven fabric when used to fabricate NCFs^[96]. Plant fibers-based fabric such as cotton fabric have been widely studied to improve their flame retardancy while keeping original properties like wash durability and flexibility^[91, 97-99]. Inspired by these, the surface treatment of plant fibers has been proposed to improve the flame retardancy of FRCs.

The modification of fiber surfaces for various purposes can be generally classified into chemical, physical, mechanical, and biological processes.^[2] Among them, surface chemical or physical modifications are widely used for improving the fire proofing properties of NFCs. While these modifications can be different, often improving flame retardancy and at least maintaining mechanical properties are sought.^[18] The main

results concerning surface modifications on natural fibers for improved fire and mechanical behavior are summarized in Table 3, and relevant results will be discussed afterwards.

Table 3. Recent advances in natural fibers chemical treatments and selection of Fire retardants.

Fiber type	Matrix	Surface modification	Fire retardant(s)	Flame retardancy	Reference
Short Corn pith fiber	PLA	Alkali	PA and tris base	LOI: +39.4%; UL 94: V2. PHRR: -21.7%; THR: -12.3%.	[100]
Short flax fiber	PLA	Chemical	Iron Phosphate/PD A	LOI: +26.1%; UL 94: V2. PHRR: -16.0%; TSP: -12.3%. UL 94: V0.	[101]
Flax fabric	PP and PLA	Alkali	Four aqueous phosphorus-containing solution	PHRR: -34.3% and -48.7%; THR: -11.2% and -84.9%.	[102]
Short flax	PLA/PP	Alkali	Four aqueous phosphorus-containing solution	UL 94: V0; PHRR: -87.0%; THR: -84.0%.	[103]
Flax fabric	phenolic resin	Alkali and Sol-gel	Flammentin TL833	PHRR: -35.6%; THR: -49.2%.	[104]
Flax fabric	Epoxy	Sol-gel	APP	UL 94: V0.	[105]
Ramie fabric	Epoxy	LbL coating	PEI / APP	LOI: +66.6%; UL 94: V0; PHRR: -69.0%; THR: -36.4%.	[106]
Ramie fabric	UPR	LbL coating	h-BN and SA	LOI: +23.0%; UL 94: V2; PHRR: -	[85]

				41.2%; THR: -17.8%. PHRR: -	
Ramie fabric	UPR	Sol-gel	TMSAP	42.2%; THR: -33.6%; UL 94: V0.	[90]
Short hemp fiber	PP	Alkali	Calcium chloride	LOI: +11.1%; UL 94: V0.	[86]
Hemp fiber	PLA	Alkali	Palonot FR	Through-depth temperatures slowed.	[107]
Short hemp fiber	UPR	Chemical	PA	LOI: +37.0%; PHRR: -	[108]
Hemp fiber	Epoxy	Alkali and Sol-gel	None	54.2%; THR: -45.3%. LOI: +4.2 and +9.3%; UL 94: NR.	[109]
Continuous Bamboo fiber	Epoxy	Alkali and physical	BA	LOI: +15.2%; PHRR: -	[96]
				33.0%; THR: -3.4%;	

3.2.1. Physical treatment on fiber surface

Plant fiber with an abundant surface functional group and inherent porosity microstructure offer ample opportunities for introducing FRs by physical approaches such as electrostatic and capillary absorptions. For instance, Kandola et al.^[103] treated flax/PP or flax/PLA commingled fiber-based fabric by four types of commercial FRs with content on the fabric between 10~13wt%. It was found that FRs in flax/PLA showed greater efficiency compared to flax/PP, which might be due to the pure hydrocarbon structure of PP. However, detrimental effects on mechanical properties, such as flexural and tensile properties, were observed. It was suggested that commercial FRs needed to be modified when imparting flame retardancy to NFCs according to matrix type as well as end applications.

Jiang et al.^[110] immersed ramie fabric into alkali-treated APP containing aqueous solution and pad-dried to get APP-absorbed ramie fabric. The treated ramie fabric was later hand-layup with epoxy resin with compression consolidation to get flame retarded NCFs. When the APP ratio reached 9wt%, the composite achieved a V0 rating in UL 94 test and an increase from 23.0% to 33.8% in terms of LOI value. The CCT results showed a 26% reduction in PHRR and a more than 40% reduction in both THR and Total smoke production (TSP). As shown in Figure 6 (a), Guo et al.^[96] treated the dignified bamboo directly with boric acid (BA) under an alkaline aqueous solution and used vacuum-assisted infusion to prepare bamboo/epoxy NCFs. The treated bamboo/epoxy composites displayed a 36% reduction of PHRR and a 15% increase of LOI value compared to that for bamboo/epoxy composite without any treatment. Khalili et al.^[111] treated plain woven jute fabric with an organic phosphonate ester or GnP separately and thereafter fabricate jute/ polyacrylic composite with fiber volume around 40%. The laminate with phosphorus-treated jute fabric (0.72wt% phosphorus content) demonstrated a 26% reduction of PHRR at a constant external heat flux of 35kW/m².

Layer-by-Layer (LbL) strategy has raised immense interest in the flame retardant field, especially in flame retardant surface treatment, mainly due to its ease of combination of different types of FR, adaptability on different surface as well as ambient processing conditions.^[112] Nevertheless, using LbL strategies to flame-retarded fiber reinforcement in FRCs previously was mainly focused on traditional fiber reinforcement^[113], with few efforts on natural fiber being reported recently^[114]. For instance, Song et al.^[106] employed LbL strategies to deploy cationic polyethyleneimine (PEI) and anionic APP dispersed in an aqueous solution to functionalize the surface of

continuous ramie fabric as shown in Figure 6 (b). After that, ramie fabric was impregnated with biobased epoxy resin with hot press consolidation to get NCFs with around 30wt% of fiber weight ratio with FRs around 5 to 10wt%. The treated Ramie/epoxy composite achieved a LOI value of 31.5 and a V0 rating under UL 94, showing enhanced flame retardancy composites with no treatment on ramie fabric. With more than 8wt% of FR on fabric, the composite after CCT at 35 kW/m² also demonstrated a reduction of more than 50% in PHRR and a more intact char layer exemplifying the condensed phase behavior.

Figure 6. (a) Graphical abstract for demonstration of absorption of boric acid by bamboo fiber and its applications in bamboo/epoxy composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[96]. Copyrights 2019 Elsevier. (b) Graphical abstract for demonstration of LbL coating on ramie fabric and its application in ramie/epoxy composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[106]. Copyrights 2023 Elsevier. (c) Scheme for demonstration of PEC coating on basalt fiber. Reproduced with permission from reference^[115]. Copyrights 2022 Elsevier.

Another promising method consisted of treating the fiber surface by polyelectrolyte complex (PEC), which forms between oppositely charged macromolecules.^[116, 117] when compared with LbL assembly, treatment with this polyelectrolyte complex involves fewer processing steps under an ambient environment. Shi et al.^[118, 119] demonstrated the possibility of carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites. Recently, Wu et al.^[115] treated basalt by dipping into PEI/PA-based PEC, as shown in Figure 6

(c). While no fire properties were screened, the investigated interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was increased by 75% compared to fiber with no treatment.

Fiber surface treatment brought the above-mentioned opportunities as well as challenges. While flame-retardant moieties were introduced on fiber surfaces, the efficacy of this method needs more comprehensive research, with many scattering reports published. What's more, natural fiber, especially plant fiber-reinforced polymer composites, tends to have lower fiber contents when produced by the LCM process, which will bring more challenges compared to traditional fiber-reinforced polymer composites.

3.2.2. Chemical treatment on fiber surface

Among chemical treatment on fiber surface, such as alkaline, silane, enzymatic, acetylation etc., has been widely used to improve compatibility and stress-transfer between reinforced fiber and polymer matrix^[105]. Alkali treatment worked by submitting the fibers into a solution of NaOH, which will break hydrogen bonds and increase their reactivity. Alao et al.^[107] chemically treated hemp fiber first with a 5% wt solution of NaOH for a variable time (1-4 h) with phosphorus and amine-containing fire-retardant spray coating lately for fabricating hemp fiber/PLA composite. The alkali treatment individually showed a slight delaying effect of Time-to-ignition (TTI). Nonetheless, alkaline treatment was not always found to be beneficial for the fire retardancy of the samples. For instance, Kandola et al. improved Flax/PP and Flax/PLA composites by adding aqueous FR solutions and noticed that pre-treatment with alkali prior to the FR treatments did not show any benefits^[102].

The sol-gel reaction or salinization for the treatment of natural fibers has been reported for improving the water resistance of fibers, enhancing the wettability of the

natural fibers surface and promoting interfacial adhesion. A combined alkali and silane treatment on both hemp and flax fiber for NFCs was recently reported by some authors^[104, 109]. Woven plain-wave flax fabric was submitted to both chemical treatments for fabric flax/epoxy composite^[104]. The TGA results of composites showed no obvious influence on the peak decomposition temperature, while the residue value was significantly increased. Short hemp fiber was treated with alkali or silane separately for preparing hemp/epoxy composites.^[109] The LOI values were slightly improved by both treatments, with a slower burning rate at horizontal burning tests when using silane treatment. In addition, alkali treatment in this work also improved mechanical properties.

Using alkali or silane treatments tends to provide little enhancement to overall fire proofing efficiency unless flame-retardant moieties are introduced. For instance, Chu et al.^[90] synthesized phosphorus and nitrogen-containing silane agent TMSAP by reaction of silane agent with Dimethyl phosphate (DMPP) and paraformaldehyde. After the sol-gel treatment on ramie fabric by TMSAP, as shown in Figure 7 (a), ramie/unsaturated polyester (UPR) composites were fabricated with fabric content of around 50wt%. While showing no rating for UL 94 test, the treated ramie/UPR laminate showed a reduction of PHRR and THR by 27% and 20% compared to those properties for untreated composite when exposed to 35 kW/m² heat flux. Zhang et al.^[108] treated short hemp fiber solely with phytic acid (PA) and later added 3wt% of hemp fiber in UPR resin composites. Nevertheless, the addition of hemp fiber showed limited fire proofing performance in terms of LOI and CCT results, which may be due to the limited uptake of PA during treatment. Yang et al.^[100] also used PA with tris base to treat corn pitch short fiber for fabricating 10wt% loaded PLA composites, as shown in Figure 7

(b). The addition of treated corn pitch fiber increased the LOI value and UL 94 ratings of blended composites. The results also showed a reduction of PHRR and THR with increased residue value.

Figure 7. (a) Graphical abstract for demonstration of sol-gel treatment with phosphorus moieties for ramié fabric and its application in ramié/UPR composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[90]. Copyrights 2018 Elsevier. (b) Graphical demonstration for phosphorus acid treatment with tris base to corn pitch fiber and its application in corn pitch fiber/ PLA composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[100]. Copyrights 2021 MDPI. (c) Demonstration of irradiation grafting of phosphorus compounds onto flax fabric. Reproduced with permission from reference^[120]. Copyrights 2022 Elsevier. (d) Graphical abstract for demonstration of flax fiber surface coating by PDA and its application in flax/PLA composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[101]. Copyrights 2018 Elsevier.

Irradiation grafting of FR provided another approach to chemically treat natural fiber without involving hydroxyl group, which was demonstrated by Sonnier^[120, 121] early by grafting dimethylvinyl phosphonates (DVP) and dimethyl (methacryloxy) methyl phosphonate (MAPC1) on the flax fabric by more than 3wt% and 0.5wt% phosphorus respectively as shown in Figure 7 (c). The grafting process gave a self-extinguishing fabric while only slight improvement when treated flax fabric were used in UPR composite. While grafting FR treatment promoted charring capabilities, it was

suggested that low fiber content (30wt%) might lead to a limited reduction of flammability for composites.^[21]

A different approach for improved FR of Flax/PLA composites comprised the use of PDA, which exhibits substrate-free adhesion properties. PDA is introduced as an innovative flame retardant which has been used on several substrates such as fabric.^[122] As shown in Figure 7 (d), a chopped 5 mm long flax fiber was first treated by dopamine self-polymerization to form a thin PDA coating on flax fiber which then formed DOPA-Fe complexes with excess ferric ions (Fe^{3+}), followed by the in-situ growth of iron phosphonate on the fiber surface^[101]. The modified flax short fiber was melt-blended with PLA to prepare NFCs with fiber content of 30wt%. The resulting NFCs showed a decrease of 21% and a 16% reduction in total smoke production and PHRR.

3.3. Fire-protective surface finishing

Another widely used approach to impart flame retardancy to NFCs is the use of fire-protective surface finishing. This method provides the minimum change during manufacturing leaving the mechanical performance almost unchanged. Various methods can be employed to apply fire-protective surface finishing, such as placing fire protective surface veil or mat before the lamination process. FRs containing polymer-based coating can also be applied either on the mold surface before fabrication of laminate or onto the surface of composite after laminate is manufactured. While numerous papers were found to apply fire protective coating on other traditional FRCs^[123-125], few efforts were found about fire protective coating on NFCs, and are mentioned below.

As shown in Figure 8 (a, b), Dou^[126] designed and prepared a UV curable acrylate-based polymer coating for short jute fiber reinforced polymer composite. A phosphate-

type functional monomer was used to increase flame retardant properties. An optimized ratio of functional monomer was found, which gave a better LOI value and decreased the horizontal burning rate. According to CCT results, the heat release curve changed into two peaks, with the first peak ascribed to the burning of flame-retardant coating.

Figure 8. (a) Scheme for surface coating of UV curable resin on jute/PP composites. (b) HRR curves for jute/PP laminate with and without different coating. Reproduced with permission from reference^[126]. Copyrights 2022 Springer Nature. (c) Digital images of the char after CCT and (d) HRR curves of ramie/ acrylic thermoplastic composite with four different types of surface finishing. Reproduced with permission from reference^[127]. Copyrights 2020 Elsevier.

Khalili^[127] tried to improve the fire safety of continuous ramie fabric reinforced acrylic thermoplastic composite by using the commercial intumescent mat, which is mainly composed of EG and ATH. Four intumescent mats with different expansion ratios were used. All four coated laminates achieved a rating of V0 in the UL 94 test. CCT results showed that TTI and, PHRR, TSP are improved obviously, with THR becoming higher, as shown in Figure 8 (c, d). The char thickness was found to be proportional to the expansion ratio of EG used in the intumescent mats.

Although fire protective coating introduced the least detrimental effects on mechanical properties, it also possesses its own disadvantage. In terms of reaction to fire properties, fire protective coating usually brings up THR due to the increase of

flammable substances. In addition, total strength-to-weight properties were also decreased due to the additional weight of fire protective coating or layers.

3.4. Integrated approaches

Besides approaching fire safety enhancement by using the individual methods mentioned above, integrating two or three methods from resin modification, fiber surface treatment as well as protective coating were also explored by several authors.

As mentioned earlier, Chu et al.^[90] treated ramie fabric with synthesized TMSAP for fabricating ramie/UPR composite. Additionally, APP was also mixed with a resin matrix with varying contents, as shown in Figure 9 (a). By combining the two methods, the treated ramie fabric/ UPR composite achieved a V0 rating and even lower PHRR and better tensile strength with less APP content than the properties of laminate without fabric treatment. In another work, Chu et al.^[85] investigated the introduction of inorganic nanomaterials into the LbL surface coating of ramie fabric. Sodium alginate (SA) anionic solution acted as a green dispersant to disperse hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) sheets, while polyethyleneimine (PEI) was used as a cationic agent. The treated ramie fabric was employed to fabricate 50wt% ramie fiber/UPR resin with and without a phosphorus-based reactive FR named PCTA. With this approach, the composite with only treated ramie fabric achieved a slight reduction in PHRR and a light improvement of LOI value. With only modified ramie fabric, an 8.2% PHRR reduction was shown in CCT results. If the content of PCTA is increased, the PHRR value is decreased up to 36% further.

As shown in Figure 9 (b), Li et al.^[73] physically treated unidirectional flax fabric with a liquid phosphorus-containing dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMPP) with a final FR content of 2, 5, 10wt%. 2wt% of montmorillonite (MMT) was added into the NFCs,

which improved LOI, UL 94 and CCT results compared to resin matrix/phenolic composite with only FRs-treated flax fabric. This was attributed to an enhancement of carbonization during combustion induced by the nanosized MMT flame retardant.

Figure 9. (a) Graphical abstract for demonstration of combining LbL coating on fabric with an additive PCTA FR for ramie/UPR composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[85]. Copyrights 2018 American Society of Chemistry. (b) Graphical abstract for demonstration of physical absorption of DMMP FR and MMT additive in resin matrix for flax/phenolic resin composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[73]. Copyrights 2022 Elsevier. (c) Scheme for surface growth of CaOH on hemp fiber. Reproduced with permission from reference^[86]. Copyrights 2017 Royal Society of Chemistry. (d) HRR curves of various surface treatment ratio on fiber surface and different additives FRs contents for flax fiber/PLA composites. Reproduced with permission from reference^[79]. Copyrights 2020 BME-PT.

Zhao et al.^[86] prepared flame-retarded short hemp fiber/PP composites by surface treatment of hemp fiber and incorporation of APP into PP matrix. The short hemp fiber was in situ grown with calcium hydroxide, as shown in Figure 9 (c). With the aid of APP, obtaining improved mechanical and fire properties. It was found that the laminate, with 50wt% of surface-modified fiber, achieved a V0 rating with 10wt% of APP. Whereas, for laminate with unmodified surface fiber, 15wt% of APP was required to

reach the same V0 rating and similar LOI values. Besides, the introduction of APP also decreased the tensile and impact strength of laminates.

Bocz et al.^[79] functionalized plain woven flax fabric with an aqueous solution named DAP/U by mixing diammonium phosphate (DAP) and urea (UA) with different ratios. Then the treated flax fabric was used with PLA to prepare NCFs with varying APP-based FR contents (0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt%). V0 rating of UL 94 tests was only achieved when both reinforcement and matrix were flame retarded. The CCT results (50kW/m²) showed that the treated flax fabric postponed T_{ig} while providing a reduction of more than 50% of PHRR and THR, as shown in Figure 9 (d). The mechanical performance was found to be improved with this combined approach suggesting the well-balanced distribution of phosphorus compound.

Employing multiple fire-retardant strategies together for NFCs offers higher potential compared to traditional fibers reinforced polymer composites. For instance, fiber surface flame retardant treatment can be easier integrated into the plant fiber's multistep extraction process^[128]. Flame retardancy and mechanical properties can be tailor-balanced to gain wider materials design flexibility as more efforts need to be demonstrated in the future.

4. Mechanical behavior under fire loads

As described in previous sections, the comparison of thermal stability between plant-based fibers and conventional fibers shows a pronounced disadvantage in terms of fire structural response, behavior and survivability^[129]. The mechanical properties of natural fibers polymer composite in an ambient environment are well known, and some excellent reviews have elaborate on these properties^[11, 130, 131]. As underlined by Kodur^[132] in a review of mechanical characterization and properties of FRPs composite

at elevated temperatures, tensile strength, elastic modulus and stress-strain relations are the mechanical properties that influence most of the fire structural capacity response of FRPs composite.

First, due to the inherent flammability of plant fiber-reinforced composites, fire retardants were usually added to improve the fire resistance of these materials and consequently influence the fire degradation behavior and mechanical properties. Nevertheless, the approaches of adding FRs in resin matrix tend to decrease the mechanical properties at ambient temperatures. Different efforts are carried out by various authors to find the best balance between avoiding the reduction of mechanical properties and improving fire structural survivability. Supparkan et al.^[133] showed how the use of MHO and ZB in a thermoplastic natural fiber composite exhibited similar tensile and flexural properties if compared with the composite without the addition of flame retardant. On the contrary, Khalili et al.^[111] compared jute/poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) with and without the use of flame retardant on jute fiber. They underlined that this kind of treatment reduces the adhesion between fiber and matrix, reducing mechanical properties. In the previous cited study of Bachtiar et al.^[83] there was also a comparative study for the effect of different types of additive flame retardant on the fire and mechanical properties of plant fibers composite. The results showed an increase in fire safety but a decrease in elastic modulus and strength which can be attributed to the agglomerate of flame-retardant particles which reduces the adhesion between fibers and matrix^[134]. An increase in terms of strain was observed, suggesting a change in the behavior of the material that results in a more ductile response.

4.1. Fire mechanical behavior for plant fiber-based NFCs.

Only a few studies were performed on the resistance and the variation of mechanical properties for plant fiber based NFCs when damaged by fire loads.^[60, 135] Bath et al.^[36] early investigated the flax/vinyl ester composite under axial tensile loading and simultaneously heat damage of two heat fluxes (10, 35 kW/m²) as shown in Figure 10 (a, b). It was found that matrix decomposition contributes much less to structural weakening compared to that of glass transition softening, mainly due to the low failure temperature. Later, Bath et al.^[60] made a comparison of fire structural response between plant fibers (jute, hemp and flax) and glass fibers reinforced vinyl ester composite as shown in Figure 10 (c, d). The glass fiber ratio was made the same as that of plant fibers for comparison. The results showed a decrease of failure stress for three plant fiber-reinforced laminates to a very lower temperature with respect to glass fiber. This was suggested to be attributed to the water loss that reduces the efficiency in the transfer of stress and due to the decreased fiber strength by some components, such as lignin, that undergo glassy to rubber transition at low temperatures^[136]. With three types of plant fibers, flax fiber showed slightly better fire structural fire performance.

Rajaei^[137] and Kim^[71] studied the effect of heat damage on post-fire/heat impact properties of flax fibers polymer composite. The first one compared between flax fibers and glass fibers, and the second compared between thermoset and thermoplastic matrix. Results showed that glass fiber composites demonstrated a rebound and an indentation if impacted after being exposed to a temperature of 300°C. Meanwhile, flax fiber panels tested in the same conditions got penetrated. Furthermore, Kim^[71], in his work, showed that a thermoplastic matrix achieved a higher impact energy with respect to a thermoset which relates to the fact that the pre-melting status of thermoplastics allowed them to

absorb more energy. In post-fire conditions, the re-solidification of the matrix is one of the key factors that permits them to achieve more impact strength compared with epoxy.

As plant fiber-based NFCs are becoming increasingly popular, these types of NFCs tend to possess inferior fire structural survivability compared to traditional FRCs. Hence, it is important to enrich the understanding of their mechanical behaviour under fire and increase their fire structural safety.

Figure 10. (a) schematic illustration and digital photos for the setting of the tensile stress rupture test. Reproduced from reference^[138]. The failure time of flax, hemp, jute fiber and glass fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites under (b) 10 kW/m² and (c) 35kW/m². Reproduced with permission from reference^[60]. Effect of applied compressive stress on failure times of (e) basalt and (f) glass laminates when exposed to the heat flux of 25 kW/m². Reproduced with permission from reference^[59]. Copyrights 2017 Elsevier. Effect of constant tensile stress on the rupture times of the basalt and glass fiber composites when exposed to heat fluxes of (g) 25 and (h) 50 kW/m². Reproduced with permission from reference^[37]. Copyrights 2015 Elsevier.

4.2. Fire mechanical behavior for mineral fiber-based NFCs.

Beyond plant-based composites, mineral-based fiber such as basalt fibers is the most used due to their high working temperature range compared to glass fibers^[139], even if it has lower tensile fire resistance mainly due to the higher emissivity which induce a fast heating process within the laminate. Bhat et al.^[37, 59] performed a comparison of compression and tensile softening and failure properties between glass and basalt fibers reinforced vinyl ester polymers when subjected to fire loads, as shown in Figure 10 (e, f, g, h). Experimental tests and analytical modelling displayed a result of diminishing

in fire structural integrity for basalt fibers. This effect was suggested to be derived from the higher absorbability compared with glass fibers which caused a faster increase of temperature inside of composite when encountered with fire. Due to this behaviour, in another study, Bath et al. tried to understand the properties of basalt fibers compared with glass and carbon fibers during a high-temperature recycling process^[140]. The study showed an obvious reduction in failure strength not connected with the degradation of fibers, but due to a growing of flaws on fibers surface, which the author attribute to the reaction of the water present in the fibers. On the other hand, the elastic modulus of fibers results was not to be affected by the recycling process.

A confirm of this behaviour was performed by Sarasini et al.^[141] which discovered a decrease in mechanical properties of recycled basalt fibers, suggesting as the cause of this phenomenon is the intrinsic degradation of basalt fibers if subjected to high temperatures. Lilli et al.^[142] using different techniques, such as a single-edge notch, to associate the loss of strength of the fibers to modifications in the structures of the materials. Results from notch tests supported the data of Sarasini^[141] about the degradation of basalt fibers subjected to high temperatures.

What's more, to better understand the impact of elevated temperature and fire loads on natural fibers, different research developed analytical and numerical models were proposed when considering the impact of these conditions' fiber reinforced polymer composite. Early, Mouritz et al.^[143] used a simple model based on the rule of mixture analysis and the values of pre-fire mechanical properties and char thickness, which predicted with good accuracy the post-fire property. Recently, Kim et al.^[19] summarized many other published models which described the fire and the post-fire

damage for composite materials. These models provided the possibility of making adequate adjustment for formulating specific models for NFCs.

One of the approaches for improving the fire structural resistance of NFCs might be by the hybridization of fiber reinforcements. Saleem et al.^[144] compared thermoplastic hybrid bast/coated basalt fibers with the same hybrid bast/glass fibers. Results showed better mechanical properties for the first one and gave a better thermal resistance compared with the total natural fibers composite. Kufel^[145] demonstrated that the use of two different kinds of natural fibers in NFCs allowed the stabilizing of thermal resistance for composite with increased thermal properties compared to composites made by one single kind of plant natural fibers. Another way to tackle the fire structural resistance challenge might be fire protective coating. Khalili et al.^[88] prepared epoxy-based coating on 20wt% short fruit fiber reinforced epoxy composites and it passed FAR required vertical Bunsen burner test results. But no mechanical properties were screened. The fire protective coating might also lead to improvement of structural survivability. Earlier, Kandare et al.^[146] presented a model to analyze the structural response of laminate with an intumescent coating. A woven glass/vinyl ester laminate with intumescent coating was used to validate the model. Due to the simplifying assumptions used in modelling, failure times predicted using the model were approximate. But both model and test validation showed that, especially at the lower stress level, the failure of insulated laminate was postponed compared to that for laminate with no insulation. This might inspire more investigations into the influence of the protective coating on the fire structural response of NFCs.

5. Summary, outlook and perspectives

5.1. Summary

Driven by the circular economy and environmental sustainability mindset from the public, NFCs are gaining increasingly bigger ground among the polymer and fiber-reinforced polymer composite industries, which in turn promote the ever-growing research efforts for fire-safe NFCs. In this review, the thermal and flammability features of natural fibers were summarized with a discussion on the influence of fiber incorporation on fire behavior of NFCs. The unique challenge of solving the flammability and fire safety of NFCs presents a multifaced problem which is addressed by on-going research efforts from the scientific community. Recent progress, especially during the last five years, is being discussed and summarized in this review to present some new perspectives and ideas for the development of fire safety research of NFCs. Several strategies are being followed to promote the fire retardancy of composites, mainly by either modification of the resin or surface treatment on the fibers as well as fire-protective surface finishing via different physicochemical methods.

5.2. Outlook and perspectives

Sustainability

With the growing environmental awareness and technological advancement, ever increasing interest are being paid to not only polymer and polymer composite materials from sustainable and recyclable resources, but also to high value additives derived from eco-benign substances. It is foreseen that more and more bio-based flame retardants will be employed in developing new generation flame-retardant NFCs, aiming to enhance sustainability and reduce the carbon footprint. However, it will face some challenges, such as flame-retardant efficiency, processability, compatibility of biobased flame retardants to the natural fiber reinforced polymers. In addition, similar to the

recycle and reuse of polymer-based products, further development and utilization of plant-based derivatives to NFCs, such as functional celluloses, lignin, etc., would be another promising approach to contribute the sustainability and circular economy.

Multifunctionalities

The diversity of natural fibers, flame retardant additives and polymer matrix offer plenty of possibility on developing multifunctional NFCs. Besides the flame retardancy and mechanical enhancement of NFCs, properties like electromagnetic shielding, thermal conductivity as well as recyclability can be further imparted to NFCs based on functionalized additives. We do believe that multifunctionalities to NFCs would be cutting-edge research in the future.

Association with machine learning

The implementation of machine learning avoids long development cycles, low efficiency and high costs of traditional materials development process which involves empirical trial and error and simulation methods. Due to the diversity and complexity of natural fibers, flame retardant additives and polymer matrix, it is foreseen that development of new generation of NFCs via associating with machine learning would be another focused topic in the future. By associating with machine learning to discover new materials, it may bring a revolutionary improvement on developing new generation NFCs.

Structural fire safety

Study on structural fire safety of NFCs is still a very challenging research topic, although some progress has been achieved in the past. Definitely, more studies need to be carried out systemically in the future, such as varied static or dynamic fire loading scenarios, fire intensity as well as their impact on flame retardancy of NFCs. Moreover,

development of novel methods to investigate the fire structural safety, in particular to establish in-situ testing approach in fire conditions would be crucial.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xiang Ao: Writing-original draft & editing, Visualization. **Antonio Vázquez-López:** Writing-original draft & editing. **Davide Mocerino:** Writing-original draft & editing. **Carlos González:** Writing-Review & Editing. **De-Yi Wang:** Conceptualization, Writing-Review & Editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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